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D14.3 Outreach and Engagement Report

Work Package	WorldFAIR D14.3 Outreach and Engagement Report
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Abbreviations and Acronyms

CDIF	Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework
CODATA	Committee on Data of the International Science Council
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
HE	Horizon Europe
HE C&E WG	Horizon Europe Communication and Engagement Working Group
IDW	International Data Week
IUPAC	International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
RDA	Research Data Alliance
SALURBAL	Salud Urbana en America Latina
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This report summarises the outreach and engagement activities of the WorldFAIR project. We describe key activities carried out throughout the funded project period, and present analytics collected on key social media, events, and the project website. The outreach and engagement activities of WorldFAIR aimed to meet two primary goals:

1. Creating a trusted brand that serves as a tacit marker of quality shared by the outputs. This trust encourages the promotion of project outputs across disciplines, both by the project staff and by the members of the project's audience groups.
2. Demonstrating that the project's outputs represent concrete and substantial contributions to the body of knowledge related to implementing the FAIR principles, particularly data reuse, within and across discipline areas. The presentation of the results needs to include considerable detail to be relevant and interesting to the disciplinary specialist, as well as to those working to advance data interoperability.

The WorldFAIR project was successful in reaching both goals. We base this assessment on the following observations:

- The highly engaged part of the project audience (mailing list recipients) opened emails at a considerably higher rate than industry averages, based on benchmarks provided by the tools used (goal 1).
- The click-through rates and participation numbers in most of the webinars were consistent with the more specialist-oriented nature of materials and events (goal 2).
- Finally, the website statistics collected could be seen as indications of how the successful branding (goal 1) seems to act as an amplifier (potentially bringing in new members to each of the sub-groups supported by the project).

The synergies between these two goals will bring in benefits even after the project. Any exploitation activity based on one of the disciplinary outputs will strengthen the project brand and increase the chances of exploitation of other disciplinary outputs. This deliverable presents the mechanisms that the outreach and engagement activities used to build these foundations for future exploitation activities.

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1. Introduction

The main objectives of the WorldFAIR dissemination plan (as defined in November 2022) were to create an efficient communication strategy and plan actions to support the needs of each of the project's eleven case study Work Packages, enabling them to reach their target audiences with their key messages.

The second aim was to create the project brand, and to establish visibility and communication channels with the relevant high-level project-wide stakeholders. Further objectives were to support the project partners by creating branding and dissemination materials needed for their own communication actions, and to document and monitor the communication actions undertaken by Work Package 14 (Outreach, sustainability and exploitation) and other project participants.

These objectives have been addressed through a series of activities and communication and outreach strategies:

- The creation of the project brand, based on the WorldFAIR petal diagram, with each petal representing a case study.
- The development of a project website based on the brand, with a dedicated space for each of the case studies detailing all key highlights of their work, and visual materials based on the brand, colour-coded according to their position on the 'petal' diagram¹.
- The creation of project promotional materials to enable the project partners to approach a wider network: these distil extensive guidelines and recommendations into concise 'two-pager' briefing documents.
- The production of visual materials that promote a key output of the WorldFAIR project, the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework², which will contribute significantly to the sustainability and uptake of results and to the continuation of the WorldFAIR legacy.
- The organisation of an engaging webinar series aiming to highlight results not only from a disciplinary perspective (i.e., not only for each 'petal') but also showcasing the wider applicability of the guidelines and recommendations across disciplines. These webinars paired speakers from different case studies together, adopted panel formats, invited 'lightning talk' presentations and created a productive venue for engaging the attendees and sparking discussions about the work of the case studies.
- Facilitating the integration of the case study WP teams in the Committee on Data of the International Science Council (CODATA) and Research Data Alliance (RDA) networks by supporting their participation in International Data Week³ and RDA Plenary⁴ meetings, which,

¹ <https://worldfair-project.eu/case-studies/>

² <https://worldfair-project.eu/cross-domain-interoperability-framework/>

³ <https://internationaldataweek.org/about-idw/>

⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/>

as shown in this analysis, significantly increased engagement with the wider Open Science community.

- The creation of a number of campaigns promoting recorded interviews and conversations between case study WP teams.

This report describes key activities carried out throughout the funding period, and presents analytics collected on key social media, events, and the project website. The document is divided in two sections: the communications activities (Section 2, outlining the creation of the visual identity, brand, materials and online presence and related analytics), and the outreach and engagement activities (section 3) centred on events and recorded materials.

2. Communications activities

The communication endeavours of the WorldFAIR project aimed to reach a broad spectrum of stakeholders by building the project's online brand and presence, and creating accessible materials so that regardless of expertise, stakeholders can grasp the project's results. The tools utilised as part of this strategy were the website, newsletters, case study cards, and engaging with audiences through social media platforms and the publication of videos.

2.1. The WorldFAIR Project website

The WorldFAIR website was originally created at project kick-off to facilitate and document the core needs of the project. As the RDA Association AISBL recruited a dedicated communications manager in late 2022, effort was dedicated to improving the brand and online identity of the project. The new website, launched in May 2023, enhances the visibility of the wealth of project outputs and activities, and the rich and diverse collection of the WorldFAIR Case Studies. The following areas were the focus of the redesign:

- Landing page, including a banner section highlighting key activities
- Dedicated page for each case study with branding redesign (Figures 2a & 2b)
- Output focus
- News and blogs section
- Creation of an Events section (Figure 3)
- Focus section on the webinar series⁵
- 'WorldFAIR in a nutshell' section summarising all key activities⁶
- Section showcasing the impact of project results (figures 1a and 1b).

⁵ <https://worldfair-project.eu/the-worldfair-project-webinar-series-presenting-project-outputs/>

⁶ <https://worldfair-project.eu/12-months-of-the-worldfair-project/>

WorldFAIR Impact & Exploitation

Each WorldFAIR case study has produced recommendations and/or a FIP for their discipline or interdisciplinary research area, and tools or approaches in their domain. The long term exploitation of WorldFAIR results has potential impact in terms of FAIR policy and practice in 11 research areas (Chemistry, Nanomaterials, Geochemistry, Social Surveys, Population Health, Urban Health, Biodiversity, Agricultural Biodiversity, Ocean Sciences, Disaster Risk Reduction and Cultural Heritage), as well as for the whole global Research Data and Open Science community by proposing the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF), which will assist interdisciplinary research.

Figure 1a. Impact overview page.

Chemistry

In the greater environment of Open Science and data-driven approaches to global challenges, access to chemical information is critical for many cross-domain research areas. Representing chemical substances in structure form is one of the most critical functions in communicating chemistry, including sharing FAIR and machine-readable chemical data. However, data resources that index chemical structures lack standardised system-to-system interoperability, which can propagate errors when exchanging and compiling chemistry data. To meet this challenge, the Chemistry case study developed a prototype web service to confirm chemical identity and provide real-time feedback on the machine readability of chemical representation based on IUPAC standard rule sets and community best practices. Data resources, software and other services that reference chemical information can implement the specified protocols based on their existing or preferred technologies (e.g., toolkits, programming languages). Users often need to consider several data resources as a part of their everyday work. There are a number of scenarios where it is useful to navigate across distributed data resources using programmatic methods – for example, a global search for specific chemicals, cross-exchange of chemical information between data repositories, validation of converted or predicted chemical representations, or integration of distributed data for compiled meta-analysis. A consistent approach for chemistry resources to expose information about the chemical representations used in their system through a common protocol as outlined in 'D3.3 Utility services for Chemistry Standards' will facilitate navigation across these resources. Individual data systems providing their associations between the IUPAC International Chemical Identifier (InChI) and their record identifiers can foster data hubs that provide one-stop shops for links to all resources relevant to a chemical structure using InChI as the cross-link.

Nanomaterials

The progression of the proposed extension of the IUPAC InChI to cover nanomaterials (and eventually also advanced materials) has been a key effort of the nanomaterials Case Study, and the submission of the formal proposal for adoption by the InChI Trust is the final step to achieve the initial version of the standard extension. Close collaboration with the InChI development team has been critical to ensuring that decisions made regarding the Nanomaterials InChI are consistent with those on the development pipeline for InChI itself. The NanoCommons User Guide and the WorldFAIR post-project sustainability activities will be important aspects of driving the adoption by databases, repositories and nanomaterials commercial providers of the Nanomaterials InChI. The convergence of the Nanomaterials InChI approach with the European regulatory approach of "nanoforms" and "sets of nanoforms" is another important driver for adoption, and a NanoOpinion on the final Nanomaterials InChI standard will be drafted for the European Chemicals Agency. Demonstrator projects to implement the first standard version of the Nanomaterials InChI have also been identified, including the Horizon Europe funded projects MACRAME, PINK, INSIGHT and CHIASMA.

Biodiversity

The Biodiversity Case Study is part of a large community-driven project to better model biodiversity data for science and policy relevance. The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) is leading the overhaul of the Darwin Core data standard used by thousands of institutions worldwide with a new GBIF Unified Data model. The WorldFAIR Case Study is a set of studies to test the model and get community input on directions and usability. GBIF, as a Global Biodata Core infrastructure, provides sustainability for this process which will take many years to complete. It is GBIF's intention that when mature, or portions of it, are mature those components will be placed before the governance of the Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) for review and ratification by the community that helped develop it.

Figure 1b. Innovation and Adoption impact website page.

The screenshot shows the 'Chemistry' page on the WorldFAIR website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'HOME', 'CASE STUDIES', 'SYNTHESIS', and 'NEWS & EVENTS'. Below the navigation bar, the word 'Chemistry' is prominently displayed. A circular diagram with various colored segments is featured, representing different aspects of the project. To the right of this diagram, a text box explains the goals of the WP3 (FAIR Chemistry) and lists key activities: developing guidelines, tools, and validation services; addressing gaps in standards; and engaging stakeholders. Below this, a paragraph discusses the importance of chemical data in various fields like climate, health, and food. The bottom section of the page is titled 'Chemistry Featured Outputs' and lists several key documents: 'IUPAC FAIR CHEMISTRY PROTOCOL SERVICES', 'DIGITAL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR CHEMISTRY FAIR DATA POLICY AND PRACTICE (D3.1)', 'TRAINING PACKAGE: FAIR CHEMISTRY COOKBOOK (D3.2)', and 'UTILITY SERVICES FOR CHEMISTRY STANDARDS (D3.3)'. Each output is accompanied by a brief description and a 'Read more' link.

The screenshot shows the 'Work Package Leads' section of the IUPAC website. At the top, the IUPAC logo is displayed in a colorful, segmented font. Below the logo, the text 'Work Package Leads' is centered. A profile picture of Leah Rae McEwen is shown next to her name and affiliation, 'Leah Rae McEwen, Cornell University'. The section below is titled 'What is a Chemical? Webinar Series' and features a promotional graphic for a virtual webinar. The graphic includes the IUPAC WorldFAIR Chemistry logo, the title 'What is a Chemical? Innovation in Chemical Descriptions', a list of speakers (Mach Types, Molosov, Omladine, Complex Substance), a moderator (Alex Clark), and a flash talk & panel discussion on February 17, 2023. A QR code and a registration link (https://bit.ly/FAIRW4) are also present. The bottom section of the page is titled 'Chemistry News' and features three news items with images and dates: 'New WorldFAIR Project reports now available' (8th March 2024), 'Low Data Week 2024' (5th March 2024), and 'New Resources for Chemicals & Chemical Data users worldwide!'.

Figures 2a & 2b. Case study branding and focus on WorldFAIR website.

<p>FRI 1</p>	<p>■ Featured December 1, 2023 @ 1:00 pm - 2:00 pm</p> <p>HMC FAIR Friday: The WorldFAIR project with Dr. Simon Hodson & Dr. Arofan Gregory</p> <p>Date: Friday, 1 December 2023, 13:00 CEST Speakers: Dr. Simon Hodson & Dr. Arofan Gregory The next lecture will take place on 1 December 2023 at 13:00 CEST featuring Dr Simon Hodson (Executive Director of CODATA) and Dr Arofan Gregory (Chair of the DDI Cross-Domain Integration working group) who introduce us to the objectives of the [...]</p>	
<p>WED 6</p>	<p>December 6, 2023 @ 9:00 am - 10:00 am</p> <p>WorldFAIR Output Webinar Series: Guidelines & Recommendations from Cultural Heritage and Social Surveys</p> <p>The following reports will be presented in this webinar: Cross-national Social Sciences survey best practice guidelines A proposed workflow for the processing of data harmonisation of social surveys, that takes account of the practical steps required to bring diverse content together in a machine-actionable way, and that could best take advantage of external registered, persistent [...]</p>	
<p>WED 6</p>	<p>December 6, 2023 @ 10:00 am - 12:00 pm</p> <p>Optimising FAIRness of federated Data Discovery & Access Service and underpinning Blue Data Infrastructures</p> <p>Times in CET TimeSessionPresenter10:00 - 10:10Introduction Blue-Cloud 2026 projectDick Schaap - MARIS & Blue-Cloud10:00 - 10:30 Data management and provision by EuroArgo -Argo ocean observing systemThierry Carval : IFREMER & Blue-Cloud10:30 - 10:35 Questions & Answers about EuroArgoAll10:35 - 10:55Data management and provision by SeaDataNet pan-European marine and ocean data management infrastructure and networkDick Schaap - MARIS [...]</p>	
<p>January 2024</p>		
<p>THU 4</p>	<p>January 4 @ 10:00 am - 11:00 am</p> <p>Cancelled: The WorldFAIR Webinar Series: Guidelines and Recommendations from the Case Studies on Geochemistry and Ocean Science & Sustainable Development</p> <p>This event has been cancelled. A new date will be released soon. About the Case Studies Geochemistry Geochemistry has applications in many disciplines including environment, resources (groundwater, minerals, energy), geohhealth, ocean, and agriculture: it is a component of many UN SDGs. Fundamental to our approach is ensuring that in networking common components across these disciplines, [...]</p>	
<p>April 2024</p>		
<p>THU 18</p>	<p>April 18 @ 2:00 pm - 3:00 pm</p> <p>The WorldFAIR webinar series: Reusing Plant-Pollinator Datasets: a Global Perspective with Guidelines and Recommendations inspired by Pilot Studies from Africa, the Americas and Europe.</p> <p>Times in UTC Agenda Case Study OverviewDebra DruckerFAIR data standardization strategyDebra DruckerLightning talks: Lessons learned from case study pilots pilotsAllObservations of plant-pollinator interactions in the Pampean region of Argentina, conducted by Facultad de Agronomia - Universidad de Buenos AiresRocio Ana González-VaqueroThe Brazilian Plant-Pollinator Interactions Network (REBIPP)José Augusto SalimThe Plant-Pollinator Interaction Data Collection by the Kenya [...]</p>	
<p>MON 22</p>	<p>April 22 @ 1:00 pm - 2:00 pm</p> <p>The WorldFAIR Webinar Series: Guidelines and Recommendations from the Case Studies on Chemistry and Nanomaterials</p> <p>Time in UTC Speakers: Evan Bolton, Protocol Services: Standardized programmatic access to chemical information Stuart Chalk, Training Cookbook: Digital recipes for managing chemical datasetsLynch: The Case Study on Nanomaterials More about the Case Studies Chemistry The WP3 (FAIR Chemistry) aims to align chemistry data standards with the FAIR data principles through: - Development of [...]</p>	

Figure 3. Events section on WorldFAIR website.

2.1.1. Website analytics

Figure 4. Geographical distribution of website visits, from Google Analytics.

Given the project’s global, cross-disciplinary nature and its international consortium bringing their own rich communities and networks on board, the WorldFAIR website has reached over 140 countries around the world. Figure 4 presents the top 7 countries from which content was accessed based on the number of website users. These analytics reflect the global reach of the project’s work, with the top country list including the US, Europe, Australasia and China.

Figure 5 presents unique website visitors from the period December 2022⁷ - May 2024. Overall, the website attracted over 13,000 unique visitors, significantly exceeding the KPI initially set for the project (1,000 visitors).

⁷ Google Analytics was set up in December 2022, when the dedicated Communications Officer was onboarded.

Figure 5. Unique website visitors, from Google Analytics.

Figure 6 lists the top 10 most viewed pages during the project's lifetime (until 24 May 2024). The first page ('1' shown as '/' in the figure) refers to the homepage⁸. It is worth highlighting that the newsletter and events pages are amongst the most visited pages, further indicating the value of the social media campaigns and usefulness of the webinar series in engaging the target communities.

⁸ <https://worldfair-project.eu/>

		↓ Views -----	Users -----	Views per user -----
		27,388 100% of total	13,111 100% of total	2.09 Avg 0%
1	/	7,906	5,741	1.38
2	/cross-domain-interoperability-framework/	1,651	1,300	1.27
3	/fair-implementation-profiles/	1,024	917	1.12
4	/the-project/	915	634	1.44
5	/case-studies/	866	718	1.21
6	/worldfair-newsletter/	646	542	1.19
7	/events/	553	386	1.43
8	/cultural-heritage/	548	366	1.50
9	/2023/04/24/worldfair-project-webinar-series-announced/	496	315	1.57
10	/chemistry-wp3/	452	304	1.49

Figure 6. Most viewed pages, from Google Analytics.

2.2. The WorldFAIR Project Newsletter

The WorldFAIR newsletter, kickstarted in December 2022, was issued monthly and coordinated by WP14 (Table 1). The project consortium contributed to content using an internal communications coordination plan.

Each newsletter highlighted the project’s activities for each month, as well as published reports, and upcoming events. Such events were either organised by the project or events the consortium was invited to present on WorldFAIR.

Table 1. List of published WorldFAIR newsletters issued throughout the lifetime of the project with related data.

	Newsletter (title & link)	Recipients	Sent date	Open rate	Click rate
1	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, December 2022	6	22/12/22	83.3%	50%
2	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter,	50	3/2/23	63.3%	20.4%

	Newsletter (title & link)	Recipients	Sent date	Open rate	Click rate
	January 2023				
3	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, February 2023	60	3/3/23	61.7%	16.7%
4	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, March 2023	62	5/4/23	51.6%	9.7%
5	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, April 2023	67	5/5/23	52.2%	16.4%
6	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, May 2023	74	6/6/23	45.9%	16.2%
7	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, June 2023	80	4/7/23	48.8%	18.8%
8	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, July 2023	81	1/8/23	44.4%	16%
9	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, August 2023	98	6/9/23	43.8%	6.3%
10	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, September 2023	100	6/10/23	44.9%	8.2%
11	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, October 2023	101	10/11/23	42.4%	6.1%
12	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, November 2023	103	8/12/23	43%	9%
13	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, December 2023	103	8/1/24	48.5%	8.1%
14	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, January 2024	104	12/2/24	53%	11%
15	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, February 2024	104	13/3/24	46.1%	13.7%

	Newsletter (title & link)	Recipients	Sent date	Open rate	Click rate
16	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, March 2024	115	15/4/24	46%	10.6%
17	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, April 2024	116	15/5/24	40.4%	7%
18	WorldFAIR Project Newsletter, April 2024	At least 116	31/5/24	Data not available at the time of writing	Data not available at the time of writing

The average click rate for the newsletter based on data up to April 2024 is 14%. This percentage is 11.4% higher than the average click rate (of 2.6%) across all industries according to Mailchimp data from 2023 (the platform used for the distribution of this newsletter)⁹. The average open rate is at

Figure 7. Project Newsletter audience growth

50.5% as opposed to the average of 34.2%, i.e., 16.3% above this benchmark. Both of these statistics,

⁹ <https://mailchimp.com/resources/email-marketing-benchmarks/>

in combination with the steady increase in subscribers, indicate the success of the newsletter in engaging its readers and conveying information.

In order to boost the number of subscribers, The initial newsletter was circulated to the project consortium, and each partner subsequently further disseminated using their networks. Links to subscribe to the newsletter were included on the WorldFAIR website. All newsletters were uploaded to the website and disseminated on social media (Figures 8a&b). Since the newsletter was initiated, it has gathered an audience of 116 members at the time of writing this report (Figure 7). This number continues to grow leading up to project end.

Figures 8a & 8b. Promotion of the newsletter on X.

2.3. Project marketing collateral

This section describes project marketing collateral (i.e., promotional materials) developed in support of the WorldFAIR activities.

2.3.1. Case study cards

To facilitate the promotion of the results published by the document to wider audiences, the work of each case study and the extensive published reports were distilled into case study cards (Figure 9), addressing the following key parts for each WP:

- What is the case study about?
- What is the challenge being addressed?

- What is the solution proposed?
- What is the impact of the work?
- Summary of recommendations.
- Example of a cross-domain use case.

Figure 9. Case study cards (printed and digital). Please access full-size versions on the project website.

The case study cards were made available in digital format on the WorldFAIR website¹⁰, distributed in print at events and conferences, and used in social media campaigns (Figure 10). Please access full-size versions of these at <https://worldfair-project.eu/communication-toolkit/case-study-cards/>.

¹⁰ <https://worldfair-project.eu/communication-toolkit/case-study-cards/#section>

Figure 10. Social media promotion of printed materials at events

2.3.2. The Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework promotional materials

At the time of writing this report, the deliverable setting out CDIF - D2.3 'Report Synthesising Recommendations for Disciplines and Cross-Disciplinary Research Areas (CDIF)', one of the key outputs of the WorldFAIR project - is still in development, with a due date of 31 May 2024. WP14 is currently liaising with WP2 (Recommendations, Synthesis and FAIR Assessment, the authors of D2.3) and graphic designers for the production of a brief based on the CDIF with enhanced graphics.

This set of communications materials will be complete in the first week of June 2024 (following completion of the CDIF report), and will be used to highlight this key output, to continue building on the WorldFAIR legacy, and to support sustainability and exploitation efforts (in particular the WorldFAIR+ initiative¹¹).

2.4. Social media campaigns

Social media channels (X (formerly Twitter), LinkedIn, Mastodon, and Facebook) were utilised for the dissemination of project results and publications, and the promotion of events. Campaigns related

¹¹ <https://worldfair-project.eu/worldfair-plus/>

to newsletter dissemination, events where the project was particularly active, and campaigns surrounding our specific initiatives (webinar series, podcast, interviews) are described in the respective sections.

Figure 11 shows the growth of the project’s engagement with the community on X since project kick-off in June 2022, and up until the end of April 2024 (the time of writing of this report).

It is worth noting that following initial outreach about project launch, subsequent activities had little traction on X until the concentrated X campaign around the project’s participation in RDA Plenary 20. This increase in engagement and account followers highlights the effectiveness of the campaign and the success of the WorldFAIR workshop co-located with RDA Plenary 20, and the case study leads’ participation in the various RDA P20 sessions. It also showcases the value of the networking event in connecting with the Open Science and research data community and the value of engaging with a diverse and global community such as the RDA.

The highest engagement rate on X is noted in June 2023, in response to the promotion of the WorldFAIR webinars on the CDIF and the FIPs produced by the project, and the meeting presenting the outputs of the WPs on Cultural Heritage and Social Surveys.

The increased engagement noted in October 2023 reflects the project’s activities in International Data Week (IDW) 2023 (Figure 11; see also section 3.3.1).

Figure 11. Impressions growth on WorldFAIR X channel.

Finally, it should also be taken into consideration that some of the partners created their own social media and webpages (for example, FAIR Chemistry^{12,13}), or utilised their institutional accounts (for example, content was often duplicated by the coordinating partner's social media accounts¹⁴) which contributed significantly to the dissemination effort. This also distributed the views and interactions, however; and data from such accounts is not included in this report.

2.5. Promotion of project results

The publication of new deliverables and articles produced by case study leads was supported by promotion campaigns using news items and the dedicated output sections on the website, mailing lists, social media posts (Figure 12) and the project newsletter, in addition to amplification of dissemination efforts led by consortium partners.

A webinar series was launched in May 2023 with the objective to raise awareness around the published project results. This event series was the main vehicle for disseminating the guidelines and recommendations produced by the project, and details of the series are outlined in Section 3.2.

Figure 12. Promotion of project outputs on X.

¹² <https://twitter.com/FairChemistry>

¹³ <https://iupac.org/project/2022-012-1-024/>

¹⁴ <https://x.com/CODATANews>, <https://www.linkedin.com/company/codata-with-icsu-committee-on-data-for-science-and-technology/>, <https://www.facebook.com/codata.org>

2.6. The podcast: WorldFAIR Conversations: Cross-Domain Interoperability and Challenges

Figure 13. Example of the promotion of the WorldFAIR podcast on Interoperability across and within domains.

Coordinated by WP14, Leah McEwen (Cornell University, WP3 Chemistry), Iseult Lynch (University of Birmingham, WP4 Nanomaterials), Kerstin Lehnert (Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory, WP5 Geochemistry) and Beth Knazook (Digital Repository of Ireland, WP13 Cultural Heritage) recorded a conversation¹⁵ about ‘Cross-Domain Interoperability and Challenges’ during IDW2023 in October 2023 in Salzburg. The WP leads discussed common challenges across their fields and how the WorldFAIR project and the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework work to resolve them (and even identify new ones).

The experts discuss topics such as collections, samples, digital and physical objects, record keeping, persistent identifiers, metadata, reusability of data, gathering use cases and much more relating to Chemistry, Nanomaterials, Geochemistry and Cultural Heritage disciplines.

The recording was converted into a podcast and distributed widely via the WorldFAIR channel, newsletter and social media channels.

¹⁵ <https://youtu.be/PGXUXYztDaU?si=nKPu0cdsd5ovZndi>

2.7. Case study lead interviews

A series of interviews with the project coordinator and leads of WPs 2, 3, 5, 6 and 10 were filmed and published via the WorldFAIR channels (Figure 14). During each interview, the case study leads discussed the impact of their work in their respective disciplines and from a cross-disciplinary perspective. The partners also discussed their next steps, their thoughts on the sustainability of the project results, and the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF).

The interviews are available on the project's YouTube channel¹⁶.

Figure 14. Example of the promotion of the WorldFAIR WP leads interviews.

¹⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/@worldfairproject/videos>

3. Outreach and engagement report

The outreach activities of the WorldFAIR project aimed to engage with the identified stakeholders by building connections with other European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)-related projects and research data communities, enabling the integration of WorldFAIR outputs into the wider Open Science community. The main tools utilised were the WorldFAIR webinar series on presenting project outputs, the participation in events lead by major project partners - CODATA and the RDA - and the amplification of case study participation in third-party events through the project networks.

3.1. Stakeholders and target audiences

The list of stakeholders and the means by which they were engaged during the project is provided in more detail in D14.4 Update Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan¹⁷. Table 2 provides a high-level overview of the communities and key stakeholders that were engaged during the funding period.

Table 2. List of stakeholders, key messages, and methods of engagement

Stakeholder / target audience	Key messages and results promoted	Channels and methods used
Individual Researchers and Research Communities	Case study guidelines, recommendations, FAIR Implementation Profiles, data standards and training materials	Social media campaigns, newsletter, WorldFAIR webinar series and participation in RDA Plenaries and International Data Week events, participation in third-party events (IDCC, LIBER)
Data Stewards and Data Managers	Case study guidelines, recommendations, FAIR Implementation Profiles, data standards and training materials	Social media campaigns, newsletter, WorldFAIR webinar series and participation in RDA Plenaries and International Data Week events

¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11205161>

Stakeholder / target audience	Key messages and results promoted	Channels and methods used
Funders	Policy briefs and contributions to the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)	Participation in EOSC Symposium and UN events, social media campaigns
Policy makers	Policy briefs and contributions to the SRIA, guidelines and recommendations relating to Disaster Risk Reduction and Public and Urban Health	Participation in EOSC Symposium and UN events, social media campaigns
Service managers that support scientists and researchers working with data and information management and communication professionals	Case study guidelines, recommendations, FAIR Implementation Profiles, data standards and training materials	Participation in events through case study networks (e.g., IUPAC, GBIF), social media campaigns
Libraries and other memory institutions, non-profit organisations, community and professional societies	Case study guidelines, recommendations, FAIR Implementation Profiles, data standards and training materials	Participation in LIBER and IDCC conferences, DRI blogs and mailing lists
Data/research initiatives	Case study guidelines, recommendations, FAIR Implementation Profiles, data standards and training materials	Social media campaigns, participation in EOSC Symposium and UN events, social media campaigns, utilisation of CODATA channels
Research software engineers / software developers	Case study guidelines, recommendations, FAIR Implementation Profiles, data standards and training materials	Participation in events through case study networks (e.g., IUPAC, GBIF)
Repositories	Case study guidelines, recommendations, FAIR	Participation in LIBER and IDCC conferences, DRI blogs and

Stakeholder / target audience	Key messages and results promoted	Channels and methods used
	Implementation Profiles, data standards and training materials	mailing lists

3.2. The WorldFAIR webinar series

The WorldFAIR Project launched a webinar series in May 2023 aiming to promote and discuss guidelines and recommendations published by the project. The webinar series was organised, coordinated, facilitated and promoted by WP14.

The series opened with a session presenting the WorldFAIR project and placing the work carried out by the case studies in the context of EOSC and the international data landscape. Speakers included Ari Asmi (RDA AISBL), Hilary Hanahoe (RDA Secretary General) and Javier López Albacete (Policy Officer, EC).

Each subsequent webinar consisted of presentations by the Work Package leads followed by a panel session and question and answer session, aiming to engage the attendees and highlight the global, cross-disciplinary nature of the project. Two webinar presenters from different case studies were selected for each meeting; this in combination with the panel format highlighted the cross-disciplinary applicability of the project’s guidelines and recommendations.

The closing meetings of the series consisted of two 2-hour long sessions, co-located with the RDA Plenary 22. The first session explored the outputs from these case studies and in particular the recommendations made. A selection of the case studies described their work and their experience of using FAIR Implementation Profiles. They articulated key recommendations for the use of metadata standards and terminologies, structured around the most important themes and issues encountered. The second session focused on one of the key outputs of WorldFAIR: the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)¹⁸.

The webinar series runs until the end of May 2024, and by the end of the project will have delivered 15 webinars.

¹⁸ <https://worldfair-project.eu/cross-domain-interoperability-framework/>

Table 3. List of webinars organised as part of the WorldFAIR series promoting project outputs.

	Webinar	Date	Registrations
1	Opening session of the WorldFAIR webinar series	26 May 2023	104
2	Overview of the projects first round of disciplinary reports: Updates from the Social Surveys and Cultural Heritage.	14 June 2023	61
3	WorldFAIR FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs), the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) – and more.	28 June 2023	125
4	Overview of the projects first round of disciplinary reports: Updates from Chemistry and Nanomaterials.	13 September 2023	91
5	Overview of the projects first round of disciplinary reports: Updates from Biodiversity and Agriculture	20 September 2023	214
6	Overview of the projects first round of disciplinary reports: Updates from Population Health and Urban Health	8 November 2023	44
7	Overview of the projects first round of disciplinary reports: Disaster Risk Reduction Updates	15 November 2023	36
8	Overview of the projects first round of disciplinary reports: Cultural Heritage and Social Surveys updates v2	6 December 2023	26
9	Reusing Plant-Pollinator Datasets: a Global Perspective with Guidelines and Recommendations inspired by Pilot Studies from Africa, the Americas and Europe.	18 April 2024	76

	Webinar	Date	Registrations
10	Guidelines and Recommendations from the Case Studies on Chemistry and Nanomaterials	22 April 2024	81
11	Final meeting of the Cultural Heritage and Social Surveys	8 May 2024	39
12	Guidelines and Recommendations from the Case Studies on Geochemistry and Disaster Risk Reduction	20 May 2024	12
13	The journey so far and next steps: Session 1 (WPs)	22 May 2024	99
14	The journey so far and next steps: Session 2 (CDIF)	23 May 2024	109
15	Guidelines and Recommendations from the Case Study on Population Health	30 May 2024	N/A at the time of writing

Table 3 lists the webinars organised as part of this series and registration data. Attendance at the webinars averaged roughly at 50%, with an indication from attendees that registration was also an expression of interest for receiving the post-event materials and recording even if they knew they were unable to attend the live meeting (which is a behaviour that has become common post-COVID with the increase in virtual events and meetings).

The geographical distribution of registrants and attendees varied and depended on the time zone of the event and the location of the partners leading the meeting, and was influenced by dissemination efforts in participating partners' local networks and communities.

The webinar series was promoted via the project's main channels including the website¹⁹ (see Figure 15), dedicated social media campaigns and mailing lists available to the consortium. Additional promotion was done by targeting relevant RDA Working and Interest Groups and Communities of Practice, reaching a global community of over 14,000 members.

¹⁹ <https://worldfair-project.eu/the-worldfair-project-webinar-series-presenting-project-outputs/>

The recordings are available on the project website²⁰ and YouTube channel²¹.

Figure 15. Example of the promotion campaigns for the WorldFAIR webinar series

3.3. Event participation and amplification

Since 2022, the project consortium has participated in a significant number of events organised both by the project and by external stakeholders. This section provides the highlights of project participation where WorldFAIR presence was significant. A more comprehensive list of presentations at third-party events can be found at the WorldFAIR newsletter archive and events web page²².

3.3.1. International Data Week (IDW) events

Multiple sessions by WP2 on the FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) and the CDIF, as well as individual WP-related sessions, took place at the International Data Week 2022 and 2022.

International Data Week 2022

International Data Week 2022 took place in June 2022 in Korea. International Data Week (IDW) combines the RDA Plenary meetings (the biannual meeting of this international member organisation working to develop and support global infrastructure facilitating data sharing and reuse) and

²⁰ <https://worldfair-project.eu/the-worldfair-project-webinar-series-presenting-project-outputs/>

²¹ <https://www.youtube.com/@worldfairproject/videos>

²² <https://worldfair-project.eu/events/>

SciDataCon (the scientific conference addressing the frontiers of data in research organised by CODATA and WDS). As always, the event brought together a global community of data scientists and data stewards; researchers from all domains; data, interoperability and informatics experts from all fields, industry leaders and policymakers. WorldFAIR partners presented the initial work and scope of the project in the following sessions:

- WorldFAIR – Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice²³
- Unique identifiers to complement metadata for the identification and grouping of complex nanomaterials²⁴
- Mapping the Global Landscape of Geochemistry Initiatives and Databases²⁵
- Challenges for Plant-Pollinator Data Standardization²⁶
- Envisioning a Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework²⁷.

International Data Week (IDW) 2023

International Data Week 2023 took place in October 2023 in Salzburg, Austria, and it saw a much more mature project offering, including numerous published guidelines and recommendations. From organising sessions dedicated to the work underway by the project, to participating and presenting on behalf of the project in various Plenary, RDA and SciDataCon sessions, the WorldFAIR project had a vibrant and distinct presence throughout the IDW2023 week with participation in over 10 sessions. WP14 organised an exhibition stand and a poster (shown in figure 16), further ensuring the visibility of the consortium's work and disseminating printed materials.

Figure 16. The WorldFAIR exhibitor booth at IDW2023

²³ <https://www.scidatacon.org/IDW-2022/sessions/439/>

²⁴ <https://www.scidatacon.org/IDW-2022/sessions/444/>

²⁵ <https://www.scidatacon.org/IDW-2022/sessions/437/>

²⁶ <https://www.scidatacon.org/IDW-2022/sessions/418/>

²⁷ <https://www.scidatacon.org/IDW-2022/sessions/438/>

Figure 17. Social media campaign on WorldFAIR at IDW2023.

During IDW2023, WP14 coordinated a collection of insights and project-related highlights, which were published on an extensive post-event report available on the WorldFAIR website²⁸. The strong project presence was promoted in real-time and post-event through an intense social media campaign (Figure 17) highlighting key points from presentations. The social media campaign aimed

²⁸ <https://worldfair-project.eu/2023/11/10/idw2023-a-festival-of-data-with-the-worldfair-project/>

to increase engagement with participants at the event, to drive session participation and therefore community discussions with regards to project outputs that were presented, but also to provide visibility to the widespread participation of the project across the multiple sessions.

3.3.2. EOSC Symposium and EOSC Winter School

Figure 18. WorldFAIR exhibitor booth at the EOSC Symposium 2023

WP14 attended the EOSC Symposium 2023 in Madrid in September with an exhibition booth (see figure 18) alongside other Horizon Europe projects. The event showcased project presentations on how EOSC can support cross-domain interoperability presenting the WorldFAIR Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework, with the speakers list including Simon Hodson (WP2, Project Coordinator), Arofan Gregory (WP2), Pier Luigi Buttigieg (WP11) and Alexander Prent (WP5).

The project's contribution to the EOSC Symposium was summarised and promoted in a blog coordinated by WP14 and published on the WorldFAIR website²⁹.

3.3.3. RDA's 10-year anniversary event series

The communications team coordinated and facilitated two WorldFAIR webinars, part of the RDA's 10-year anniversary event series³⁰.

Table 4. List of webinars as part of the RDA 10-year anniversary series

Webinar	Date	Registration data
WorldFAIR @ RDA's 10 Year Anniversary: Image sharing systems and practices in Cultural Heritage (WP13) ³¹	28 February 2023	N/A ³²
WorldFAIR @ RDA'S 10 Year Anniversary: The WorldFAIR Case Study on Plant-pollinator Interactions (WP10) ³³	22 August 2023	151

In addition to promotional efforts by WP14, the coordinator, and the consortium, the events were disseminated through the RDA's channels by the RDA Secretariat through their monthly newsletter, group page posts and social media. The WP10 and WP13 case study leads that participated in the series also took part in the closing session of the series and were featured in the published highlights report³⁴.

²⁹ <https://worldfair-project.eu/2023/10/05/cross-domain-interoperability-use-cases-reflections-from-the-eosc-symposium-2023/>

³⁰ <https://archive.rd-alliance.org/plenaries-events/events/decade-data-celebrating-10-years-research-data-alliance>

³¹ <https://worldfair-project.eu/2023/05/18/worldfair-rdas-10-year-anniversary-image-sharing-systems-and-practices-in-cultural-heritage-2/>

³² Meeting held using a zoom account for which data is no longer available.

³³ <https://worldfair-project.eu/event/rescheduled-worldfair-rdas-10-year-anniversary-the-worldfair-case-study-on-plant-pollinator-interactions-wp10/>

³⁴ <https://my.visme.co/view/w49x0o4z-celebrating-a-decade-of-data-the-rda-039-s-10th-anniversary-highlights#s1>

3.3.4. RDA Plenary 20

 WorldFAIR project @WorldfairP · Mar 20, 2023
#WorldFAIR coordinator @simonhodson99 kicks off today's event 'The WorldFAIR Project's Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework', co-located with #RDAPlenary 20!

🗨️ 4 🔄 4 ❤️ 10 📊 364 📌 📤

Figure 19. Social Media campaign promoting WorldFAIR at RDA P20.

WorldFAIR case studies presented during RDA P20 in Sweden in March 2023, the highlights of which were published on a blog on the project website³⁵. Preceding the main plenary days, a co-located event took place on the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework³⁶, which was intensely promoted with a social media campaign (Figure 19) aiming to raise awareness on the project-related sessions that would follow, and therefore increase attendance and engagement with over 600 attendees present at the event in Sweden.

³⁵ <https://worldfair-project.eu/2023/04/14/worldfair-at-rda-plenary-20-synopsis/>

³⁶ <https://codata.org/worldfair-projects-cross-domain-interoperability-framework-workshop-20-march-2023-registration-open/>

 WorldFAIR project @WorldfairP · Mar 20, 2023 ...
 Ari Asmi @asmi_ari @RDA_Europe Director welcomes us to an exclusive joint #WorldFAIR, @EOSCFuture and @resdatall networking reception! We look forward to a week of collaborations and exploring synergies at #RDAPlenary 20!

 3
 15
 579

Figure 20. WorldFAIR/EOSC Future networking event at RDA P20.

A networking event followed the CDIF workshop, co-organised with the RDA/EOSC Future Domain Ambassador programme³⁷. The social event included activities introducing WorldFAIR case study leads to related RDA/EOSC Future Domain Ambassadors, aiming to create a connection between project representatives, RDA attendees and the EOSC Future project and community.

3.3.5. Amplification of case study initiatives

WorldFAIR case study leads have been very active in participating in various events in their respective disciplines, communities and countries, often using their own social media channels, newsletters and mailing lists.

³⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-disciplines/rda-europe-ambassadors-2022>

WP14 has been collecting this information in the communications plan, during monthly WP leads calls and through monitoring of social media activity. Such activities have been consistently amplified through project channels (Figure 21).

 WorldFAIR project @WorldfairP · May 4, 2023 ...
 #WorldFAIR's Bapon Fakhruddin will join this panel on harnessing technologies, data and knowledge for #disasterriskreduction at #irdr. More info [👉 irdrinternational.org/news/943](https://irdrinternational.org/news/943)
[@shmfakhruddin](#)

Figure 21. Amplification of participation in third party events.

4. Monitoring and performance report

This section reports on communications milestones and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) set in December 2022 as part of Deliverable 14.1³⁸. Then we report views and downloads for the WorldFAIR Zenodo Community³⁹.

4.1. Milestone and KPI progress report

Table 5. WorldFAIR Communications milestones

Communicati on milestone	Task Description	Due Date (month)	Progress report
1	Interviews promoting the 11 case studies professionally produced and disseminated through available channels (website, social media, etc.)	12	Partially completed: 5 interviews and 1 podcast completed. This activity constrained by WP leads' availability.
2	Minimum of 2 press releases and/or articles for the duration of the project	24	Completed 2 press releases available on the communication kit ⁴⁰
3	Creation of four social media accounts (LinkedIn, Twitter/X, YouTube, Facebook)	6	Completed: LinkedIn ⁴¹ , Twitter/X ⁴² , YouTube ⁴³ , Facebook ⁴⁴ Mastodon ⁴⁵
4	Minimum of 10 webinars promoting the work of the case studies	24	Exceeded: 15 webinars completed
5	2 webinars throughout the lifetime of the project aimed at communications professionals within case study networks aligning strategies and activities	24	KPI removed, as the purpose was fulfilled through the Horizon Europe Communications and Engagement Working Group (HE

³⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7327705>

³⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/worldfair-project/>

⁴⁰ <https://worldfair-project.eu/communication-toolkit/>

⁴¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/worldfair-project>

⁴² <https://twitter.com/WorldfairP>

⁴³ <https://www.youtube.com/@worldfairproject/videos>

⁴⁴ <https://www.facebook.com/WorldFAIRProject>

⁴⁵ <https://mastodon.social/@WorldFAIRProject>

Communicati on milestone	Task Description	Due Date (month)	Progress report
			C&E WG) ⁴⁶
6	5 WorldFAIR workshops organised at different stages of the project to provide updates, collect feedback and validation on findings and recommendations	24	Completed, examples: Dagstuhl Workshop “Interoperability for Cross-Domain Research: Machine-Actionability & Scalability” ⁴⁷ , 2nd FAIR Convergence Symposium in Leiden, in October 2022 ⁴⁸ , The WorldFAIR Project’s Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework’, RDA Plenary 20 and virtually ⁴⁹ , IDW2022 and 2023 (multiple) ⁵⁰
7	Dissemination via 5 national, European or international associations contributing to FAIR strategic agendas	24	Completed: Dissemination took place via the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC), CODATA, RDA, Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), Salud Urbana en America Latina (SALURBAL) project (among others)

The communications milestones identified at project launch have been met. Milestone 1 referred to interviews with WP leads was partially completed; this is partly due to effort limitation, but mostly because the objective was met through the recorded podcast with multiple case study leads, and the 15 webinars discussing each case study’s results. Milestone 5 was not pursued, as the objective was met through the monthly meetings of the Horizon Europe Communication and Engagement Working Group (HE C&E WG), which facilitated the alignment and regular liaison between communications

⁴⁶ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/winter-school-2024/joint-communications-outreach-activities-at-the-winter-school/>

⁴⁷ <https://worldfair-project.eu/2022/09/22/summary-report-dagstuhl-interoperability-for-cross-domain-research-machine-actionability-scalability-workshop/>

⁴⁸ <https://codata.org/events/conferences/fair-convergence-symposium-2022/fips-in-worldfair-what-have-we-learnt/>

⁴⁹ <https://vimeo.com/810101492>

⁵⁰ <https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/worldfair/>

professionals working across the HE projects. It is worth highlighting the success towards milestone 4, with 15 webinars promoting project results which attracted over 200 attendees.

With regards to milestone 3, it should be noted that the most successful means of communicating project activity remains X (Twitter). WorldFAIR Mastodon and Facebook accounts were created in an attempt to explore alternative routes, as initial assessments indicated that a part of the Open Science community moved away from X. The Mastodon account only attracted 5 followers and Facebook, 21 followers. The latter was created in order to engage a sizable community on plant pollination, but as it concerned only one of the 11 case studies, the overall engagement impact has been limited.

Table 6. WorldFAIR Communications KPIs

Key Performance Indicator	Observation Method	KPI Target number	Progress report
Average content items per month in social media or website	Self-reporting	5	Completed across social media and website channels
Presentation of WorldFAIR in third party events during the project	Self-reporting	5	Completed, examples ⁵¹ : RDA Plenary 20 ⁵² , IDW2023 (multiple sessions) ⁵³ , EO SC Symposium 2023 ⁵⁴ , 10 years of RDA event series ⁵⁵ , HMC FAIR Friday ⁵⁶ , 52nd LIBER Annual Conference ⁵⁷ , European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC) ⁵⁸ International Love Data

⁵¹ More information on project presence in third party events can be found on the monthly newsletters:

<https://worldfair-project.eu/worldfair-newsletter/>

⁵² <https://worldfair-project.eu/2023/04/14/worldfair-at-rda-plenary-20-synopsis/>

⁵³ <https://worldfair-project.eu/2023/11/10/idw2023-a-festival-of-data-with-the-worldfair-project/>

⁵⁴ <https://worldfair-project.eu/2023/10/05/cross-domain-interoperability-use-cases-reflections-from-the-eosc-symposium-2023/>

⁵⁵ <https://worldfair-project.eu/2023/05/18/worldfair-rdas-10-year-anniversary-image-sharing-systems-and-practices-in-cultural-heritage-2/>

⁵⁶ <https://worldfair-project.eu/2024/02/10/hmc-fair-friday-with-dr-simon-hodson-dr-arofan-gregory-recording-available/>

⁵⁷ <https://worldfair-project.eu/2023/07/31/dri-receives-the-liber-award-for-library-innovation/>

⁵⁸ <https://worldfair-project.eu/2023/01/31/webinar-series-organised-by-the-european-partnership-for-the-assessment-of-risks-from-chemicals-parc/>

			Week, February 12-16, 2024 ⁵⁹ , OneGeochemistry: Towards a Global Network of Geochemical Data at EGU2023 ⁶⁰
Unique website visits to WorldFAIR Website	Website statistics	5,000	KPI met and surpassed with over 13,000 unique visits to the website
Total downloads on the Zenodo repository of WorldFAIR outputs	Website statistics	5,000	KPI met and surpassed with 11,648 downloads and 19,795 views at the end of April 2024, (see also Annex 1). N.B. This statistic is before the publication of final deliverables including the key project report on CDIF.

With regards to downloads on the WorldFAIR Zenodo community, it is important to highlight that overall, for published deliverables and milestones, the community has a total of 11,648 downloads and 19,795 views across the 45 documents as of end of April 2024. This statistic is before the publication of final deliverables including the key project report on CDIF.

This number of views and downloads reported here can be considered an indication of the project's impact overall, and also of the effectiveness of communications and engagement activities. Most importantly, it constitutes a considerable collection of cross-disciplinary resources for data professionals that will remain available to the community beyond the end of the funding period. For more information, please see Annex 1.

⁵⁹ <https://worldfair-project.eu/2024/02/12/international-love-data-week-february-12-16-2024/>

⁶⁰ <https://worldfair-project.eu/2023/04/12/onegeochemistry-towards-a-global-network-of-geochemical-data-at-egu2023/>

Table 7. Most viewed WorldFAIR reports

Title and Link	Views	Downloads
WorldFAIR Project (D2.1) 'FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) in WorldFAIR: What Have We Learnt?'	2850	1208
WorldFAIR Project (D13.1) Cultural Heritage Mapping Report: Practices and policies supporting Cultural Heritage image sharing platforms	2377	955
WorldFAIR Project (D13.2) Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations Report	2376	917
WorldFAIR Project (D6.1) Cross-national Social Sciences survey FAIR implementation case studies	1418	634
WorldFAIR Project (D1.3) First policy brief	1143	592
WorldFAIR Project (D11.1) An assessment of the Ocean Data priority areas for development and implementation roadmap	810	414
Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) Working Documents	555	331
WorldFAIR Project (D9.1) Data standard for sharing ecological and environmental monitoring data documented for community review	495	373
WorldFAIR Project (M3): FAIR Implementation Profile Workshop	483	233

5. Conclusion

The WorldFAIR Project's communication and engagement team had the challenging task of disseminating this rich and innovative collection of guidelines, recommendations, standards and training materials produced by WorldFAIR. An international and cross-disciplinary project, WorldFAIR brought together data professionals across many fields, and engaged with a wide range of stakeholders. This required plural and flexible approaches to communication and engagement.

The WorldFAIR communication plan and strategy achieved its objective to establish a brand and an engaged community, as shown in website and social media statistics presented in this report. The high download and view rates on the Zenodo community are an indication of this successful engagement, of the overall impact of the project and the interest around the outputs of the 11 case studies and the CDIF, and most importantly, these will remain as a valuable collection of resources for the research data and open science community that will support ongoing and future efforts after the end of the project to make data FAIR and interoperable across diverse domains.

Annex

WorldFAIR Zenodo Community views per deliverable/milestone, in order of date of publication (oldest to newest). Restricted publications (e.g., the WorldFAIR Project (M2) Graphic design and project identity) and presentation slide decks have not been included).

Title and Link	Views	Downloads
WorldFAIR Project - Announcement of project launch	74	53
WorldFAIR Project (MS1) Kick-off meeting: press release	433	156
WorldFAIR Project (M3): FAIR Implementation Profile Workshop	483	233
WorldFAIR Project (D2.1) 'FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) in WorldFAIR: What Have We Learnt?'	2850	1208
WorldFAIR Project (D5.1) Formalisation of OneGeochemistry	308	204
WorldFAIR Project (D14.1) WorldFAIR Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan (living document)	126	93
WorldFAIR Project (MS5): WorldFAIR Communication Toolkit	48	45
WorldFAIR Project (D1.2) Data Management Plan (Living document v1.0)	108	114
WorldFAIR Project (D6.1) Cross-national Social Sciences survey FAIR implementation case studies	1447	634
Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) Working Documents	555	331
WorldFAIR Project (D13.1) Cultural Heritage Mapping Report: Practices and policies supporting Cultural Heritage image sharing platforms	2377	955
WorldFAIR Project (D11.1) An assessment of the Ocean Data priority areas for development and implementation roadmap	810	414
WorldFAIR Project (D1.3) First policy brief	1143	592
WorldFAIR Project (D9.1) Data standard for sharing ecological and environmental monitoring data documented for community review	495	373
The WorldFAIR Project: Making Cultural Heritage Data FAIR at the Digital Repository of Ireland	108	85

WorldFAIR Project (D13.2) Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations Report	2376	917
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